

As geopolitical lines are shifting, world regions want to become less dependent on the rest of the world.

The race for sovereignty

By KOEN DE BOSSCHERE

After decades of globalization, the world has discovered that a globalized economy has its weaknesses too, especially if supply chains pass through regions that face production issues (due to a pandemic, a local conflict, natural disaster, social unrest, energy or water shortage, geopolitical tensions, sanctions, ...). Local governments are making supply chains more resilient by shortening them, especially for products that are considered of strategic value (like chips, drugs, food, energy, ...).

But shortening supply chains brings its own challenges and is anything but self-evident.

- It might make goods more expensive due to the higher labour costs in Europe
- It means that Europe has to import raw materials instead of products, and that supply chains will have to be rerouted. There will be fierce international competition for scarce raw materials. It also means that Europe will also need more energy and water (process water, cooling, irrigation for local food production, ...) in order to support industrial activities
- Digital sovereignty means that Europe also needs to have control over strategically important software stacks and platforms. Essential European software infrastructure should not break if a major information and communication technology (ICT) company fails, or if a foreign government decides to limit the use of a platform in Europe
- The European labour market is losing one million workers per year, that is, almost 0.5% of the EU work force. Reshoring manufacturing will require workers that are also needed in the health sector (ageing population), in education, and in the renewable energy sector (which is considered Europe's growth strategy). A productive local work force is essential for sovereignty.
- Some production facilities like semiconductor fabs require highly specialized workers. Since higher education needs 10 years (engineering degree + PhD) to produce such profiles, reskilling, upskilling or immigration will be needed in the short term. The European Pact for Skills provides support for reskilling and upskilling for the green and digital transformations.

This chapter contains four contributions.

- *“The position of Europe in the world”*
This article contains a strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats analysis (SWOT) of Europe. The biggest strength of Europe is its research, and its biggest weakness is its inability to bring the results of this excellent research to the market. Its biggest threat is its rapidly shrinking work force, and the biggest opportunity is that the future growth in digital technology will be in automotive, industrial automation and cybersecurity – three of the strengths of Europe.
- *“Open source is the enabler for innovation and collaboration”*
Open source has become a global framework, but can only work well if there is enough support to help the stakeholders to do open source the right way. It is an opportunity for Europe to promote collaboration in major application domains and between academia and industry. Successful European open-source projects will not only contribute to Europe's competitiveness, but also to Europe's soft power.
- *“Europe's need for digital essentials, individual sovereignty and consumer protection”*
This article focuses on software sovereignty. It states that we should not only try to become technologically independent of countries like Russia, or China, but also of the US, and not only for hardware, but also (and especially) for software. For that to happen, the article advocates “digital essentials” that would ensure that digital functionality and services keep working no matter what happens at the geopolitical level. It states that working software is as important as food and pharmaceutical drugs for society.
- *“Rethinking education”*
The European educational system is very old and of excellent quality, but it might no longer be adapted to the needs of the 21st century. In order to be ready for the job market, graduates should have a T-shaped profile, solid technical training in a discipline supplemented with a broad set of soft skills, and a strong attitude towards lifelong learning.

Key insights

- Europe's global economic impact is dwindling because other regions are growing faster due to their demographics, rapid economic development, or abundance of natural resources.
- A major long-term challenge for Europe is to sustain economic growth with a shrinking active population (up to 0.5% per year) and growing costs for social security. Maintaining the current standard of living will require a highly educated and productive workforce.
- Bringing back critical value chains to Europe is a huge challenge: supply chains have to be rerouted, and a qualified work force needs to be trained. This is a challenge in a shrinking labour market.
- European higher education is of high quality, widely accessible, and affordable.
- Europe is a scientific powerhouse, but it fails to bring its research results to the market due to the lack of entrepreneurial talent, venture capital and a large enough IT workforce.
- Europe currently lacks digital sovereignty, both in hardware and in software. Modern IT systems are mostly made of components that are produced and controlled outside the EU.
- Open source is a global framework for collaboration and innovation that can help Europe to better collaborate and innovate, and to build soft power.
- The European Chips Act wants to strengthen chip manufacturing in Europe, and get 20% of the global chip market by 2030. This is a very ambitious goal under the constraints just mentioned.
- Digital sovereignty requires that Europe's essential software infrastructure keeps working no matter what happens outside Europe (e.g. the bankruptcy of a major IT company or interference by a foreign government).

Key recommendations

- The creation of well-funded European competence centres will help to retain and attract top talent, and to stay at the forefront of new digital technologies.
- Europe should continue to invest heavily in research and innovation, and in a more entrepreneurial Europe that generates lots of start-ups, scale-ups and global companies. Europe needs more venture capital to support the growth of scale-ups. The European Innovation Council (EIC) could be instrumental in this area.
- Europe should invest in future-proof areas like the silver economy, health, mobility, energy, automation and sustainability, and secure a global leading position in these areas.
- Europe should strive for digital sovereignty, both in hardware and in software because digital technology is the cornerstone of modern society. The goal is not to strive for full digital independence, but for at least digital interdependence with the other global regions.
- Europe should also work on "digital essentials" that can guarantee that Europe's essential software infrastructure keeps working uninterruptedly no matter what happens outside Europe.
- Europe should promote open source and create an infrastructure to support the open-source software and hardware supply chain in Europe. Open source helps collaboration and innovation, as well as building soft power.
- Higher education should pick up two additional important roles: lifelong learning and supporting regional entrepreneurial ecosystems.

Koen De Bosschere is a professor in the electronics department of Ghent University, Ghent, Belgium.

This document is part of the HiPEAC Vision available at hipec.net/vision.

This is release v.1, January 2023.

Cite as: K. De Bosschere. The race for sovereignty. In M. Duranton et al., editors, HiPEAC Vision 2023, pages 154-155, Jan 2023.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7461929

The HiPEAC project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 871174.

© HiPEAC 2023

